

Clinical validation of large-scale functional assays: CanVIG-UK recommendations for truthset assembly based on 2122 gene-truthset-assay evaluations

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Abstract (345 words)

Background:

Clear guidance is lacking regarding selection of ‘truthset’ variants to be used in clinical validation of functional assays, in particular ensuring reliable assay predictiveness for missense variants. Surveys indicate that inconsistency in clinical validation of assays reduces confidence amongst diagnostic scientists in leveraging large-scale functional assays to advance clinical variant classification.

Methods:

We firstly reviewed 112 sets of ClinGen gene-specific classification specifications (CSPECs) to assess variability in methodology for truthset assembly and clinical validation of assays

We then delineated how truthsets of ClinVar classifications might variously be assembled, applying differing rules regarding variant type and stringency of classification. We further considered options for truthset augmentation with additional benign missense variants systematically-generated using ACMG/AMP rules (of differing stringencies). In total, these constituted 70 basic approaches to ClinVar-based truthset construction. We applied these for each of *VHL*, *BRCA1*, *BRCA2* and *RAD51C*, censoring ClinVar for the date of assay publication. We additionally analysed how differing phenotypes for ClinVar classification submissions impacted truthset size.

We then performed clinical validation of five large-scale multiplexed functional assays for *VHL*, *BRCA1*, *BRCA2*, and *RAD51C* using these truthsets. We also performed clinical validations against secondary thresholds of deleteriousness-neutrality, which were published for two of the assays.

Results

The ACMG-evidence-points (ACMG-EPs) for clinical validation of each assay varied widely according to which truthset was used. For example, examining 700 ClinVar-based truthsets against *VHL* assay outputs for 2,268 variants, ACMG-EPs for pathogenicity ranged from 0.62 (no evidence) to 7.31 (strong evidence) and for benignity from -1.50 (supporting evidence) to -4.29 EPs (strong evidence). Truthsets comprising just missense variants typically resulted in lower EPs than nonsense-synonymous variants, more due to paucity of variants than lack of concordance. Truthsets based on more stringent ClinVar classifications or tighter phenotypic alignment typically improved concordance but lacked variant numbers.

Conclusions

Limited numbers of ClinVar missense classifications, especially of benignity, has been perceived as limiting. Assay validation should apply truthsets of missense-only variants, but loss of power can be mitigated by augmentation with systematically-generated benign missense variants and selection of whichever missense truthset optimises ACMG-EPs. Pathogenicity and benignity validation should be considered separately.

Introduction (3853 total)

Incorporation of functional data within clinical variant classification has historically involved varying practice regarding assay calibration, clinical validation and evidence weighting. The ACMG/AMP standards published in 2015 (v3) articulated recommendations regarding assessment of how closely the assay reflected the *in vivo* environment, and validation and robustness of the data outputs, surmising that, a “well-established, robust, validated assay” was considered suitable for ‘strong’ evidence in variant classification(1). In 2020, this guidance was further specified by the ClinGen Sequence Variant Interpretation group (Brnich et al), producing a quantitative framework for validation of assay outputs against previously classified variant ‘controls’ or ‘truthsets’ (hereafter termed Brnich-validation framework)(2). Depending on the

number of pathogenic/benign ‘truthset’ variants with assay readouts of functionally abnormal/functionally normal respectively, via the Brnich-validation framework two numeric assay-level evidence scores (Odds-Path or Likelihood Ratios) are generated, one for performance in predicting pathogenicity and one for benignity, which correspond with the ACMG/AMP Evidence points (ACMG-EPs). With regard to assembly of these ‘truthset’ (control) variants, Brnich et al state broadly that “controls should also be relevant to the disease mechanism (such as gain-of-function or loss-of-function) and the type of variant under consideration (e.g., missense controls for evaluating missense variants of uncertain significance)”(2).

Clinical validation of a new assay may be performed by the Variant Curation Expert Group (VCEP), where one exists for the gene. Otherwise, clinical end-users are reliant on metrics provided by assay-authors or else are required to perform validation themselves. Increasingly large volumes functional data from multiplex assays of variant effects (MAVEs) are being generated and offer opportunity to impact substantially on variant classification. However, lack of clarity, transparency and consistency in the stipulations and standards for validation truthsets represents a major hurdle for clinical diagnostic laboratories is using these MAVE data(3-5).

We thus sought to explore the extent and impact of variability in truthset assembly. We first reviewed the Criteria Specification (**CSpec**) Registry for 112 gene guidelines, to examine the approach adopted by 39 VCEPs for truthset assembly applied for clinical validation of functional assays.

We next sought to examine more systematically the impact on ACMG-EPs for assay-level clinical validation of variant type, stringency of classification and phenotype against which variant was classified, using truthsets assembled exclusively from ClinVar. We also evaluated augmentation of ClinVar-extracted variants with additional truthset variants systematically-generated via ACMG/AMPv3.0-based classifications.

We recognised the inherently paradoxical nature of this endeavour, namely that we would be evaluating the performance of truthsets of varying natures (and thus veracity regarding ‘the actual truth’) by using the assay outputs as a standard of truth (rather than vice versa, the intended relationship). As such, we focused first on a gene-assay dyad for which (i) there is a single presumptive mechanism of pathogenicity of loss-of-function, and (ii) high discriminatory performance of the assay had been demonstrated orthogonally. We thus selected an assay recently published by Buckley et al for which assay of HAP1 survival with Saturation Genome Editing (SGE) of the *VHL* gene had exhibited near-perfect concordance against ‘biologically-defined’ truthsets of *VHL* variants (namely variants recurrently mutated somatically in renal tumours (for pathogenicity) or variants observed recurrently in population datasets (for benignity))(6). Furthermore, mutation of the *VHL* gene is associated with well-delineated phenotypes, namely Von Hippel Lindau cancer predisposition syndrome of various subtypes and Chuvash polycythaemia. We then went on to perform similar examination of truthset assembly methodology for additional gene-assay dyads, selecting other presumptive loss-of-function cancer susceptibility genes *BRCA1*, *BRCA2* and *RAD51C* for which large-scale mutational scans have been performed using SGE(7-10).

Methods

Criteria Specification (CSpec) Registry Review

CSpec pages and associated publications were reviewed for 112 genes across 39 VCEPs on 15th December 2025. For each set of guidelines, PS3 and BS3 were reviewed for a) if the VCEP recommend application of the functional evidence codes, b) if any assays have been recommended by the VCEP, and c) if the VCEP have provided information on the variant set(s) used to validate the assays.

Functional Assay Data sources

Function scores for 2,268 variants and author-defined ‘biological truthsets’ were sourced from Buckley et al, 2024, defined as previously published(6). Function scores were also sourced for 3,893 *BRCA1*, 7,302 *BRCA2* (6,551 from Sahu et al., 2025, 6,959 from Huang et al., 2025) and 10,694 *RAD51C* variants assayed as previously published.(7-10)

All variants were annotated with the following information: variant information from Ensembl Variant Effect Predictor (VEP)(11) (v111) using the respective MANE Select transcript (*VHL*: ENST00000256474, *BRCA1*: ENST00000357654, *BRCA2*: ENST00000380152, *RAD51C*: ENST00000337432), population data from gnomAD v4.1(12), and predictive scores from REVEL(13), BayesDel noAF(14), and SpliceAI(15).

Systematically-classified variant ‘truthsets’

We systematically-classified pathogenic truncating variants, and benign synonymous and missense variants. Truncating variants were defined as variants with an Ensembl VEP consequence including “stop_gained”, “splice_acceptor_variant”, “splice_donor_variant”, “frameshift_variant”, or “start_lost”, with a REVEL score ≥ 0.644 or BayesDel noAF score ≥ 0.13 (16), and met the criteria for both PM2 and PVS1 per the respective variant curation expert groups (ClinGen *VHL* VCEP v1.1.0 (<https://cspec.genome.network/cspect/ui/svi/affiliation/50036>, ClinGen *BRCA1* and *BRCA2* VCEP v1.2.0 (<https://cspec.genome.network/cspect/ui/svi/affiliation/50087>), draft ClinGen *RAD51C* VCEP (<https://cspec.genome.network/cspect/ui/svi/affiliation/50039>)). Synonymous variants were defined as variants with a “synonymous_variant” VEP consequence and a maximum Splice AI score ≤ 0.1 .

Missense variants were defined as variants with a “missense_variant” VEP consequence. Benign missense variants were further defined using the methodology and inclusion criteria presented previously(17), using the thresholds as defined by the respective gene VCEP, and the allele

frequency threshold for BS1_sup defined as half of the allele frequency threshold for BS1. The following rules identified four sets of benign missense variant controls (with a minimum requirement of 2 observations in gnomAD v4.1 for a variant to be included in any truthset):

- Level 1: Attains BA1 (*VHL*: AF \geq 0.0156%; *BRCA1*: AF \geq 0.0868%; *BRCA2*: AF \geq 0.0906%; *RAD51C*: AF \geq 0.0583%) in any non-founder population in gnomAD v4.1
- Level 2: Attains BS1_strong (*VHL*: AF \geq 0.00156%; *BRCA1*: AF \geq 0.00868%; *BRCA2*: AF \geq 0.00906%; *RAD51C*: AF \geq 0.00583%) in any non-founder population in gnomAD v4.1 and benign evidence from either REVEL (\leq 0.183) or BayesDel noAF (\leq -0.18) using the Pejaver thresholds for benign evidence(16).
- Level 3: Attains BS1_sup (*VHL*: AF \geq 0.00078%; *BRCA1*: AF \geq 0.00434%; *BRCA2*: AF \geq 0.00453%; *RAD51C*: AF \geq 0.00292%) in any non-founder population in gnomAD v4.1 **and** benign evidence from at least one predictive tool.
- Level 4: Attains BS1_sup (*VHL*: AF \geq 0.00078%; *BRCA1*: AF \geq 0.00434%; *BRCA2*: AF \geq 0.00453%; *RAD51C*: AF \geq 0.00292%) in any non-founder population in gnomAD v4.1 **and/or** benign evidence from at least one predictive tool.

ClinVar-classified variant 'truthsets'

ClinVar variant data was censored at the most recent data archive available prior to assay publication date to ensure classifications did not incorporate functional data from the assay (*VHL*: 30/06/2024; *BRCA1*: 05/08/2018; *BRCA2*: 06/01/2025 for both assays; *RAD51C*: 01/10/2024)(18). 941 *VHL*, 913 *BRCA1*, 2,751 *BRCA2* (Sahu et al), 2,872 *BRCA2* (Huang et al), and 2,118 *RAD51C* variants were identified with both a ClinVar classification and corresponding assay function (Table S1). Analyses were also repeated for all genes using ClinVar variant data downloaded on 2nd June 2025(18) (Table S2).

Assay-level clinical validation

Using the author-provided thresholds for functionally normal and functionally abnormal, clinical calibration/validation was conducted using the approach described by Brnich et al., 2020(2), with one addition to introduce a level of caution by distinguishing between true and false positive and negative results when calculating the posterior probability:

For pathogenicity: True Positives / (All functionally abnormal results + 1)

For benignity: (False negatives +1) / (All functionally normal results + 1)

The OddsPath towards pathogenicity (PS3) and benignity (BS3) was then calculated as per Tavtigian et al(19), where P_1 is the prior probability and P_2 is the posterior probability:

$$[P_2 \times (1 - P_1)] / [(1 - P_2) \times P_1]$$

OddsPath were then categorised according to ACMG/AMP v3 evidence strength categories by log transforming to base 2.08(20) (where supporting evidence in either direction = 1 point, moderate = 2 points, strong = 4 points, and very strong = 8 points).

Assay specificity_{pathogenicity} was calculated as the number of functionally abnormal pathogenic variants / (total number of pathogenic variants – pathogenic variants with an intermediate function score) and sensitivity_{pathogenicity} as the number of functionally abnormal benign variants / (total benign variants – intermediate benign variants).

Results

Approaches to truthset construction adopted by VCEPs

On review of 112 gene guidelines, 94% (105/112) allowed PS3 and 55% (62/112) allow BS3 application. Where functional evidence was allowed, 75% (79/105) recommended specific functional assays, of which variant sets used in validation were elucidated for only 56% (44/79) of guidelines (Table S3). The source for variants used in validation varied widely (curated by VCEP:

25% (11/44), used variants from the publication: 18% (8/44), ClinVar only: 5% (2/44), multifactorial-analyses: 5% (2/44), identified in cases: 2% (1/44), other variant databases: 2% (1/44)). Information regarding provenance was not provided for the majority of guidelines where variant sets were provided (52%, 23/44).

Permutations of truthset assembly

Using ClinVar-extracted variants only, by combining enumerations of variant type (all versus nonsense-synonymous-only versus missense-only), classification stringency including class (P and B only versus P/LP and B/LB) and number of stars (any* versus $\geq 1^*$ versus $\geq 2^*$ versus $\geq 3^*$), we recognised 24 immediate approaches by which truthsets could be assembled. For 0^* and 1^* P/LP and B/LB classifications, ClinVar assignments might include or not include ‘soft conflicts’ (e.g. VUS vs LB or VUS vs LP), increasing this total to 30 approaches. For the ten ‘missense-only’ approaches, ClinVar-extracted benign missense variants could be augmented by systematically-ACMG-classified truthset variants, which we generated applying four levels of stringency (although more are of course possible), thus increasing to 70 the tally ClinVar-based approaches for truthset assembly.

ClinVar classifications for *VHL* had been submitted against 36 phenotypes (with additional permutations extractable from the free text, namely Type 1 and Type 2 Von Hippel Lindau Syndrome). Considering five phenotypes for variant submission, namely (i) any (or no) phenotype (ii) any ‘*VHL* syndrome’ phenotype and (iii) ‘Type 1 *VHL* syndrome’, (iv) ‘Type 2 *VHL* syndrome’, and (v) Chuvash Polycythaemia, the number of approaches for ClinVar-based truthset construction for *VHL* variants was scaled from 70 to 350.

We then applied these 350 truthsets to the assay outputs for the 2,268 *VHL* variants generated by Buckley et al, using the Brnich-validation framework to generate ACMG-EPs. Concurrently we calculated specificity_{pathogenicity} and sensitivity_{pathogenicity} for calling a variant as pathogenic: these

measures quantify concordance between the assay and the truthset but are not influenced by power (truthset size) or the ratio of available truthset variants (benign:pathogenic).

Bench-marking using the orthogonal author-supplied ‘biological’ *VHL* truthsets (based on somatic observations (for pathogenicity) and presence in population datasets (for benignity)): for ‘all variants’ the assay attained ACMG-EPs of 6.3 for pathogenicity and -6.4 for benignity exhibiting perfect concordance (specificity_{pathogenicity} of 100% and sensitivity_{pathogenicity} of 100%). When restricted to missense variants, the assay attained ACMG-EPs of 4.8 (pathogenicity) and -5.7 (benignity), with specificity_{pathogenicity} of 98% and sensitivity_{pathogenicity} of 100%. Applying to *VHL* assay outputs the truthsets of systematically-classified nonsense plus synonymous variant, this yielded ACMG-EPs of 5.6 for pathogenicity and -4.2 for benignity (with specificity_{pathogenicity} of 99% and sensitivity_{pathogenicity} of 97%) (Tables 1, S1). These metrics affirmed the high standards of performance of this assay.

Table 1: Comparison of systematically-ACMG-classified nonsense-synonymous truthsets against ClinVar-derived truthsets of different variant type.

Gene	Variant Type	Source (pathogenic)	Source (benign)	ClinVar class	ClinVar Soft Conflicts	ClinVar stars	No. pathogenic controls	No. benign controls	specificity _{pathogenicity}	sensitivity _{pathogenicity}	Balanced accuracy	Abnormal, Pathogenic	Abnormal, Benign	Intermediate, Pathogenic	Intermediate, Benign	Neutral, Pathogenic	Neutral, Benign	EP_PS3	EP_BS3
VHL	All	Biological truthset(1)	Biological truthset(1)	NA	NA	NA	120	108	0.00	1.00	1.00	120	0	0	7	0	101	6.39	-6.45
	Missense	Biological truthset(1)	Biological truthset(1)	NA	NA	NA	73	99	0.02	1.00	0.99	73	2	0	10	0	87	4.77	-5.68
	PTVs + Syn	Sys-ACMG-classified(2)	Sys-ACMG-classified(3)	NA	NA	NA	68	369	0.01	0.97	0.98	66	5	0	10	2	354	5.58	-4.20
	PTVs + Syn	ClinVar	ClinVar	P/LP and B/LB	Yes	≥1	48	189	0.03	0.96	0.97	46	5	0	5	2	179	4.65	-3.71
	Missense	ClinVar	ClinVar	P/LP and B/LB	Yes	≥1	181	25	0.04	0.78	0.87	133	1	11	1	37	23	3.03	-2.02
	All	ClinVar	ClinVar	P/LP and B/LB	Yes	≥1	241	270	0.03	0.82	0.89	186	8	13	13	42	249	4.29	-2.24
BRCA1	PTVs + Syn	Sys-ACMG-classified(2)	Sys-ACMG-classified(3)	NA	NA	NA	45	504	0.00	1.00	1.00	45	2	0	8	0	494	7.00	-5.17
	PTVs + Syn	ClinVar	ClinVar	P/LP and B/LB	Yes	≥1	166	130	0.01	0.97	0.98	156	1	5	5	5	124	5.62	-4.47
	Missense	ClinVar	ClinVar	P/LP and B/LB	Yes	≥1	90	40	0.03	0.96	0.97	81	1	6	0	3	39	3.95	-4.22
	All	ClinVar	ClinVar	P/LP and B/LB	Yes	≥1	287	257	0.01	0.96	0.98	265	3	12	6	10	248	5.58	-4.40
BRCA2 (Sahu et al)	PTVs + Syn	Sys-ACMG-classified(2)	Sys-ACMG-classified(3)	NA	NA	NA	228	1251	0.07	0.96	0.94	213	83	5	45	10	1123	3.59	-3.99
	PTVs + Syn	ClinVar	ClinVar	P/LP and B/LB	Yes	≥1	279	559	0.06	0.92	0.93	246	31	11	23	22	505	3.73	-3.27
	Missense	ClinVar	ClinVar	P/LP and B/LB	Yes	≥1	121	321	0.07	0.91	0.92	106	20	5	16	10	285	3.54	-3.11
	All	ClinVar	ClinVar	P/LP and B/LB	Yes	≥1	429	904	0.06	0.92	0.93	378	54	17	39	34	811	3.65	-3.27
BRCA2 (Huang et al)	PTVs + Syn	Sys-ACMG-classified(2)	Sys-ACMG-classified(3)	NA	NA	NA	357	1265	0.00	0.98	0.99	349	2	2	1	6	1262	8.22	-5.37
	PTVs + Syn	ClinVar	ClinVar	P/LP and B/LB	Yes	≥1	304	571	0.00	0.98	0.99	296	2	2	3	6	566	7.13	-5.14
	Missense	ClinVar	ClinVar	P/LP and B/LB	Yes	≥1	116	310	0.05	0.96	0.96	109	16	3	3	4	291	3.88	-4.21
	All	ClinVar	ClinVar	P/LP and B/LB	Yes	≥1	453	994	0.02	0.98	0.98	437	20	5	13	11	961	5.22	-4.91
RAD51C	PTVs + Syn	Sys-ACMG-classified(2)	Sys-ACMG-classified(3)	NA	NA	NA	131	1599	0.02	0.93	0.95	122	38	NA	NA	9	1561	4.97	-3.48
	PTVs + Syn	ClinVar	ClinVar	P/LP and B/LB	Yes	≥1	213	527	0.02	0.98	0.98	209	9	NA	NA	4	518	5.39	-5.10
	Missense	ClinVar	ClinVar	P/LP and B/LB	Yes	≥1	29	108	0.06	0.86	0.90	25	6	NA	NA	4	102	3.53	-2.32
	All	ClinVar	ClinVar	P/LP and B/LB	Yes	≥1	261	835	0.03	0.97	0.97	253	25	NA	NA	8	810	4.69	-4.56

PTV=Protein Truncating Variant; Syn = Synonymous variant; P/LP=Pathogenic or Likely Pathogenic; B/LB=Benign or Likely Benign; EP=Evidence Points. (1) Biological truthsets

consist of variants identified using cBioPortal assembled by the assay authors in Buckley et al., 2024. (2) Systematically-ACMG-classified: Truncating variant which is eligible

for PVS1 and PM2 per VCEP specifications, and attains predictive evidence towards pathogenicity (using REVEL or BayesDel, noAF). (3) Systematically-ACMG-classified:

Synonymous variant per protein impact, and maximum SpliceAI score is ≤0.1.

Using ClinVar VHL classifications (censored at the date of assay publication), ACMG-EPs for the 350 ClinVar-based VHL truthset assembly approaches ranged from 0.62 EPs (no evidence) to 5.6 EPs (strong evidence) for pathogenicity and -1.5 EPs (supporting evidence) to -4.29 EPs (strong evidence) for benignity.

For the four *BRCA1*, *BRCA2* and *RAD51C* assays we did not have equivalent ‘biological’ truthsets: gross evaluation of assay performance was thus reliant on observed concordance of assay outputs against “systematically-classified” nonsense-synonymous truthsets (Table 1). Overall the assays demonstrated strong concordance with these truthsets. The *BRCA2* Sahu et al. assay exhibited the poorest specificity_{pathogenicity} (93%) and the *RAD51C* assay poorest for sensitivity_{pathogenicity}(93%). Using ClinVar data (censored at the respective dates of assay publication), these gene-assay dyads likewise exhibit comparably wide ranges in ACMG-EPs (EPs) across the 70 approaches to ClinVar-based truthset assembly explored (Tables 1-3, Table S1)

Table 2: Comparison of ClinVar-derived truthsets comprising missense variants only.

Gene	Variant Type	ClinVar class	ClinVar Soft Conflicts	ClinVar stars	No. pathogenic controls	No. benign controls	specificity _{pathogenicity}	sensitivity _{pathogenicity}	Balanced accuracy	Abnormal, Pathogenic	Abnormal, Benign	Intermediate, Pathogenic	Intermediate, Benign	Neutral, Pathogenic	Neutral, Benign	EP_PS3	EP_BS3
VHL	Missense	P/LP and B/LB	Yes	Any	194	25	0.04	0.76	0.86	139	1	12	1	43	23	2.99	-1.91
	Missense	P/LP and B/LB	No	Any	155	2	0.00	0.84	0.92	122	0	9	1	24	1	NA	NA
	Missense	P and B	No	Any	106	0	NA	0.93	NA	94	0	5	0	7	0	NA	NA
	Missense	P/LP and B/LB	Yes	≥1	181	25	0.04	0.78	0.87	133	1	11	1	37	23	3.03	-2.02
	Missense	P/LP and B/LB	No	≥1	142	2	0.00	0.87	0.93	116	0	8	1	18	1	NA	NA
	Missense	P/LP and B/LB	No	≥2	83	1	NA	0.96	NA	75	0	5	1	3	0	NA	NA
	Missense	P and B	No	≥2	74	0	NA	0.96	NA	66	0	5	0	3	0	NA	NA
	Missense	P/LP and B/LB	No	≥3	0	0	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
BRCA1	Missense	P/LP and B/LB	Yes	Any	91	40	0.03	0.96	0.97	82	1	6	0	3	39	3.95	-4.23
	Missense	P/LP and B/LB	No	Any	71	18	0.06	0.96	0.95	64	1	4	0	3	17	2.86	-3.85
	Missense	P and B	No	Any	38	12	0.08	0.94	0.93	33	1	3	0	2	11	2.25	-3.35
	Missense	P/LP and B/LB	Yes	≥1	90	40	0.03	0.96	0.97	81	1	6	0	3	39	3.95	-4.22
	Missense	P/LP and B/LB	No	≥1	70	18	0.06	0.95	0.95	63	1	4	0	3	17	2.86	-3.83
	Missense	P/LP and B/LB	No	≥2	44	14	0.07	0.98	0.95	43	1	0	0	1	13	2.63	-4.12
	Missense	P and B	No	≥2	28	12	0.08	0.96	0.94	27	1	0	0	1	11	2.40	-3.48
	Missense	P/LP and B/LB	No	≥3	20	12	0.08	0.95	0.93	19	1	0	0	1	11	2.38	-3.03
BRCA2 (Sahu et al 2025)	Missense	P/LP and B/LB	Yes	Any	122	323	0.07	0.91	0.92	106	20	5	17	11	286	3.54	-3.00
	Missense	P/LP and B/LB	No	Any	70	53	0.04	0.90	0.93	61	2	2	2	7	49	3.73	-2.85
	Missense	P and B	No	Any	18	25	0.04	0.82	0.89	14	1	1	2	3	22	3.11	-1.88
	Missense	P/LP and B/LB	Yes	≥1	121	321	0.07	0.91	0.92	106	20	5	16	10	285	3.54	-3.11
	Missense	P/LP and B/LB	No	≥1	69	51	0.04	0.91	0.94	61	2	2	1	6	48	3.70	-3.04
	Missense	P/LP and B/LB	No	≥2	50	29	0.04	0.90	0.93	43	1	2	1	5	27	3.45	-2.80
	Missense	P and B	No	≥2	14	22	0.05	0.77	0.86	10	1	1	1	3	20	2.81	-1.58
	Missense	P/LP and B/LB	No	≥3	13	22	0.05	0.75	0.85	9	1	1	1	3	20	2.77	-1.48
BRCA2 (Huang et al 2025)	Missense	P/LP and B/LB	Yes	Any	118	312	0.05	0.95	0.95	109	16	3	3	6	293	3.86	-3.77
	Missense	P/LP and B/LB	No	Any	68	52	0.06	0.92	0.93	61	3	2	1	5	48	3.35	-3.21
	Missense	P and B	No	Any	19	27	0.04	0.94	0.95	17	1	1	0	1	26	3.40	-3.02
	Missense	P/LP and B/LB	Yes	≥1	116	310	0.05	0.96	0.96	109	16	3	3	4	291	3.88	-4.21
	Missense	P/LP and B/LB	No	≥1	66	50	0.06	0.95	0.95	61	3	2	1	3	46	3.34	-3.71
	Missense	P/LP and B/LB	No	≥2	47	30	0.03	0.96	0.96	44	1	1	0	2	29	3.61	-3.71
	Missense	P and B	No	≥2	14	24	0.04	1.00	0.98	13	1	1	0	0	23	3.29	-3.55
	Missense	P/LP and B/LB	No	≥3	13	24	0.04	1.00	0.98	12	1	1	0	0	23	3.28	-3.44
RAD51C	Missense	P/LP and B/LB	Yes	Any	29	108	0.06	0.86	0.90	25	6	0	0	4	102	3.53	-2.32
	Missense	P/LP and B/LB	No	Any	9	14	0.07	1.00	0.96	9	1	0	0	0	13	2.66	-2.90
	Missense	P and B	No	Any	0	1	0.00	NA	NA	0	0	0	0	0	1	NA	NA
	Missense	P/LP and B/LB	Yes	≥1	29	108	0.06	0.86	0.90	25	6	0	0	4	102	3.53	-2.32
	Missense	P/LP and B/LB	No	≥1	9	14	0.07	1.00	0.96	9	1	0	0	0	13	2.66	-2.90
	Missense	P/LP and B/LB	No	≥2	8	2	0.00	1.00	1.00	8	0	0	0	0	2	0.95	-2.84
	Missense	P and B	No	≥2	0	0	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
	Missense	P/LP and B/LB	No	≥3	0	0	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

P=Pathogenic; LP=Likely Pathogenic; LB=Likely Benign; B=Benign; EP=Evidence Points. NA=not calculable.

Table 3: Comparison of ClinVar-based missense truthsets supplemented by systematically-ACMG-classified benign missense variants.

Gene	Source (benign)	ClinVar class	ClinVar Soft Conflicts	ClinVar stars	No. pathogenic controls	No. benign controls	specificity _{pathogenicity}	sensitivity _{pathogenicity}	Balanced accuracy	Abnormal, Pathogenic	Abnormal, Benign	Intermediate, Pathogenic	Intermediate, Benign	Neutral, Pathogenic	Neutral, Benign	EP_PS3	EP_BS3
VHL	Systematically-ACMG-classified 1	P/LP and B/LB	Yes	≥1	181	27	0.04	0.78	0.87	133	1	11	2	37	24	3.13	-1.97
	Systematically-ACMG-classified 2	P/LP and B/LB	Yes	≥1	181	35	0.03	0.78	0.88	133	1	11	3	37	31	3.49	-1.97
	Systematically-ACMG-classified 3	P/LP and B/LB	Yes	≥1	181	35	0.03	0.78	0.88	133	1	11	3	37	31	3.49	-1.97
	Systematically-ACMG-classified 4	P/LP and B/LB	Yes	≥1	181	206	0.04	0.78	0.87	133	7	11	15	37	184	4.01	-1.98
BRCA1	Systematically-ACMG-classified 1	P/LP and B/LB	Yes	≥1	90	40	0.03	0.96	0.97	81	1	6	0	3	39	3.95	-4.22
	Systematically-ACMG-classified 2	P/LP and B/LB	Yes	≥1	90	45	0.02	0.96	0.97	81	1	6	1	3	43	4.11	-4.19
	Systematically-ACMG-classified 3	P/LP and B/LB	Yes	≥1	90	47	0.02	0.96	0.97	81	1	6	2	3	44	4.17	-4.16
	Systematically-ACMG-classified 4	P/LP and B/LB	Yes	≥1	90	1115	0.03	0.96	0.97	81	28	6	59	3	1028	4.84	-4.14
BRCA2 (Sahu et al)	Systematically-ACMG-classified 1	P/LP and B/LB	Yes	≥1	121	321	0.07	0.91	0.92	106	20	5	16	10	285	3.54	-3.11
	Systematically-ACMG-classified 2	P/LP and B/LB	Yes	≥1	121	326	0.07	0.91	0.92	106	22	5	17	10	287	3.44	-3.10
	Systematically-ACMG-classified 3	P/LP and B/LB	Yes	≥1	121	347	0.08	0.91	0.92	106	25	5	19	10	303	3.36	-3.09
	Systematically-ACMG-classified 4	P/LP and B/LB	Yes	≥1	121	3571	0.10	0.91	0.90	106	352	5	200	10	3019	2.98	-3.04
BRCA2 (Huang et al)	Systematically-ACMG-classified 1	P/LP and B/LB	Yes	≥1	116	310	0.05	0.96	0.96	109	16	3	3	4	291	3.88	-4.21
	Systematically-ACMG-classified 2	P/LP and B/LB	Yes	≥1	116	311	0.05	0.96	0.96	109	16	3	3	4	292	3.88	-4.21
	Systematically-ACMG-classified 3	P/LP and B/LB	Yes	≥1	116	316	0.05	0.96	0.96	109	16	3	3	4	297	3.91	-4.21
	Systematically-ACMG-classified 4	P/LP and B/LB	Yes	≥1	116	1311	0.03	0.96	0.97	109	44	3	13	4	1254	4.52	-4.23
RAD51C	Systematically-ACMG-classified 1	P/LP and B/LB	Yes	≥1	29	109	0.06	0.86	0.90	25	6	0	0	4	103	3.55	-2.32
	Systematically-ACMG-classified 2	P/LP and B/LB	Yes	≥1	29	126	0.06	0.86	0.90	25	7	0	0	4	119	3.56	-2.32
	Systematically-ACMG-classified 3	P/LP and B/LB	Yes	≥1	29	146	0.08	0.86	0.89	25	11	0	0	4	135	3.21	-2.29
	Systematically-ACMG-classified 4	P/LP and B/LB	Yes	≥1	29	1682	0.11	0.86	0.88	25	183	0	0	4	1499	2.82	-2.24

P/LP=Pathogenic or Likely Pathogenic; B/LB=Benign or Likely Benign; EP=Evidence Points. (1) Attains BA1 in any non-founder population in gnomAD v4.1. (2) Attains BS1_strong in any non-founder population in gnomAD v4.1 and benign evidence from either REVEL (≤ 0.183) or BayesDel noAF (≤ -0.18). (3) Attains BS1_sup in any non-founder population in gnomAD v4.1 and benign evidence from at least one predictive tool. (4) Attains BS1_sup in any non-founder population in gnomAD v4.1 and/or benign evidence from at least one predictive tool.

Influence of variant type

We examined truthsets extracted from ClinVar comprising three 'variant type' groupings (i) just nonsense and synonymous variants, (ii) just missense variants, or (iii) all available variants. Considering all phenotypes and ≥ 1 star classifications of P/LP or B/LB, for *VHL* the concordance measures (sensitivity/specificity) are modestly lower for missense compared to nonsense-synonymous truthsets (with 'all' variants being intermediate). For missense-only truthsets, this lower concordance in conjunction with smaller number of available Clinvar-extracted benign missense truthset variants resulted in lower ACMG-EPs_{pathogenicity}. Patterns of results for *BRCA1*, *BRCA2* and *RAD51C* assays were broadly similar to *VHL*, influenced by the relative preponderance in ClinVar classifications for nonsense-synonymous versus missense variants (Table 1).

Influence of stringency of ClinVar classifications

We explored three metrics of classification stringency applicable to ClinVar extraction: classification strength (i.e. likely pathogenic vs pathogenic), number of submitters (i.e. number of stars) and allowance/non-allowance of soft-conflicts in underlying submitted classifications (i.e. variant classified as VUS by one submitter and LB by another) (Table 2, Table S1).

For all assays examined, allowance of soft-conflicts dramatically increases available benignity-missense-truthset-variants, thus significantly enhancing the Brnich-evidence score_{pathogenicity} for missense-only clinical validation. Notably, the sensitivity_{pathogenicity} was generally more compromised, consistent with soft conflicts in classification of pathogenicity more often allowing inclusion of erroneous classifications. Specificity_{pathogenicity} was little changed suggesting soft-conflicts for benignity were less likely to indicate erroneous classifications. Stringency regarding (i) P/B versus P+LP/B+LB or (ii) higher number of stars resulted in modest improvement in concordance (sensitivity/specificity) but resulted in dramatic diminution in number of truthset variants. Thus greater stringency generally resulted in lower Brnich-evidence scores (EPs)

Influence of stringency for systematically-classified benign missense variants

We examined augmentation of ClinVar-extracted classifications with systematically-generated ACMG/AMPv3.0-based classifications for benign *VHL* missense variants. We explored four levels of stringency by which benignity was defined, relating to both population allele frequency and in silico predictions. As anticipated, applying more stringent thresholds for systematic generation of benignity classification resulted improved concordance (namely specificity_{pathogenicity}), whilst more permissive thresholds improved the number of variants generated. Overall these influences broadly balanced out regarding the Brnich-evidence scores (EPs) for pathogenicity, with different optimal points of trade-off for each gene examined.

Influence of phenotype

When ‘truthsets’ were restricted to *VHL* variants for which pathogenicity classifications were reported against a more specific phenotype, namely ‘*VHL* syndrome’ or ‘Type 1 *VHL* syndrome’ this improved the concordance; the resultant Brnich-evidence scores (EPs) were also modestly improved despite reduced numbers of pathogenic truthset variants (Table 4).

Table 4: Comparison of ClinVar-derived truthsets of all VHL variants using different phenotype associations

Gene	Variant Type	ClinVar class	ClinVar Soft Conflicts	ClinVar stars	ClinVar Phenotype	No. pathogenic controls	No. benign controls	specificity _{pathogenicity}	sensitivity _{pathogenicity}	Balanced accuracy	Abnormal, Pathogenic	Abnormal, Benign	Intermediate, Pathogenic	Intermediate, Benign	Neutral, Pathogenic	Neutral, Benign	EP_PS3	EP_BS3
VHL	All	P/LP and B/LB	Yes	≥1	Any	241	270	0.03	0.82	0.89	186	8	13	13	42	249	4.29	-2.24
	All	P/LP and B/LB	Yes	≥1	von Hippel-Lindau Syndrome	222	246	0.03	0.81	0.89	170	6	12	12	40	228	4.50	-2.20
	All	P/LP and B/LB	Yes	≥1	Type 1 von Hippel-Lindau Syndrome	7	246	0.03	0.86	0.92	6	6	0	12	1	228	4.65	-1.61
	All	P/LP and B/LB	Yes	≥1	Type 2 von Hippel-Lindau Syndrome	21	246	0.03	0.89	0.93	16	6	3	12	2	228	4.49	-2.55
	All	P/LP and B/LB	Yes	≥1	Chuvash Polycythaemia	177	242	0.02	0.77	0.87	128	5	11	12	38	225	4.61	-1.97

P/LP=Pathogenic or Likely Pathogenic; B/LB=Benign or Likely Benign; EP=Evidence Points.

Influence of deleterious score range for assay output

For both the *VHL* and *RAD51C* assays, the authors had delineated two zones within the deleterious score range. For *VHL* these zones were entitled LOF1 and LOF2; for *RAD51C* the zones were entitled ‘fast-depletion’ and ‘slow-depletion’. As anticipated, restricting to the more extreme scoring zone for deleteriousness improved concordance and Brnich-evidence scores (EPs), but would result in a lower proportion of variants assigned as deleterious with more variants assigned to the indeterminate zone (Table 5).

Table 5: Comparison of truthsets for VHL and RAD51C, with the function score zone for variants considered deleterious (Loss Of Function, LOF) defined using different thresholds

Gene	LOF zone	Variant Type	Source (pathogenic)	Source (benign)	ClinVar class	ClinVar Soft Conflicts	ClinVar stars	No. pathogenic controls	No. benign controls	specificity _{pathogenicity}	sensitivity _{pathogenicity}	Balanced accuracy	Abnormal, Pathogenic	Abnormal, Benign	Intermediate, Pathogenic	Intermediate, Benign	Neutral, Pathogenic	Neutral, Benign	EP_PS3	EP_BS3
VHL	LOF1 + LOF2	PTVs + Syn	Sys-ACMG-classified(1)	Sys-ACMG-classified(2)	NA	NA	NA	68	369	0.01	0.97	0.98	66	5	0	10	2	354	5.58	-4.20
		PTVs + Syn	ClinVar	ClinVar	P/LP and B/LB	Yes	≥1	48	189	0.03	0.96	0.97	46	5	0	5	2	179	4.65	-3.71
		Missense	ClinVar	ClinVar	P/LP and B/LB	Yes	≥1	181	25	0.04	0.78	0.87	133	1	11	1	37	23	3.03	-2.02
		All	ClinVar	ClinVar	P/LP and B/LB	Yes	≥1	241	270	0.03	0.82	0.89	186	8	13	13	42	249	4.29	-2.24
	LOF1 only	PTVs + Syn	Sys-ACMG-classified(1)	Sys-ACMG-classified(2)	NA	NA	NA	68	369	0.00	0.97	0.98	63	0	3	15	2	354	7.97	-4.20
		All	ClinVar	ClinVar	P/LP and B/LB	Yes	≥1	241	270	0.00	0.77	0.88	140	0	59	21	42	249	6.90	-2.24
		Missense	ClinVar	ClinVar	P/LP and B/LB	Yes	≥1	181	25	0.00	0.71	0.86	92	0	52	2	37	23	3.47	-2.02
		PTVs + Syn	ClinVar	ClinVar	P/LP and B/LB	Yes	≥1	48	189	0.00	0.96	0.98	44	0	2	10	2	179	7.04	-3.71
RAD51C	Fast + Slow depleters	PTVs + Syn	Sys-ACMG-classified(1)	Sys-ACMG-classified(2)	NA	NA	NA	131	1599	0.02	0.93	0.95	122	38	NA	NA	9	1561	4.97	-3.48
		PTVs + Syn	ClinVar	ClinVar	P/LP and B/LB	Yes	≥1	213	527	0.02	0.98	0.98	209	9	NA	NA	4	518	5.39	-5.10
		Missense	ClinVar	ClinVar	P/LP and B/LB	Yes	≥1	29	108	0.06	0.86	0.90	25	6	NA	NA	4	102	3.53	-2.32
		All	ClinVar	ClinVar	P/LP and B/LB	Yes	≥1	261	835	0.03	0.97	0.97	253	25	NA	NA	8	810	4.69	-4.56
	Fast depleters only	PTVs + Syn	Sys-ACMG-classified(1)	Sys-ACMG-classified(2)	NA	NA	NA	131	1599	0.01	0.93	0.96	120	22	2	16	9	1561	5.67	-3.48
		All	ClinVar	ClinVar	P/LP and B/LB	Yes	≥1	261	835	0.02	0.97	0.98	243	13	10	12	8	810	5.48	-4.56
		Missense	ClinVar	ClinVar	P/LP and B/LB	Yes	≥1	29	108	0.03	0.83	0.90	19	3	6	3	4	102	3.92	-2.32
		PTVs + Syn	ClinVar	ClinVar	P/LP and B/LB	Yes	≥1	213	527	0.01	0.98	0.99	207	3	2	6	4	518	6.63	-5.10

PTV=Protein Truncating Variant; Syn = Synonymous variant; P/LP=Pathogenic or Likely Pathogenic; B/LB=Benign or Likely Benign; EP=Evidence Points. (1) Systematically-ACMG-classified: Truncating variant which is eligible for PVS1 and PM2 per VCEP specifications, and attains predictive evidence towards pathogenicity (using REVEL or BayesDel, noAF). (2) Systematically-ACMG-classified: Synonymous variant per protein impact, and maximum SpliceAI score is ≤0.1.

Influence of censoring date of ClinVar extraction

For our primary analysis we used a ClinVar extract contemporaneous to the date of assay publication; however we repeated the analyses using classifications extracted from ClinVar at the time of analysis (01/06/2025, Table S2). As might be predicted, in particular for the *BRCA1* assay published in 2018, there was a marked increase in the number of available missense variant classifications for both pathogenicity and benignity truthsets. Furthermore, a higher number of variants had attained P/B classification (rather than LP/LB) and an increased proportion of variants had attained 2* and 3* classifications. There was also higher concordance between truthset classifications and assay outputs for missense variants using the more recent ClinVar extract, as would be anticipated if assay data had contributed to these more recent classifications.

Discussion

We have examined in total 2,122 truthset-gene-assay combinations to explore the impact on Brnich-assay-validation of different approaches to assembly of pathogenicity/benignity truthsets. Firstly, we demonstrate the large number of approaches to assembling truthsets that are possible using just ClinVar-extracted variants, via application of different stipulations regarding variant type and classification stringency. We then illustrate the additional permutations resultant from specifying the phenotype against which the ClinVar classifications were submitted, and additional permutations from augmenting ClinVar classifications with systematically-classified nonsense, synonymous, and benign missense variants (applying different levels of stringency).

Secondly, we demonstrate how application of these different truthsets to Brnich-assay-validation can result in widely varying Brnich-evidence scores (EPs), exploring in detail the large-scale SGE data for *VHL* generated by Buckley et al (validated as highly predictive using independent clinical-

biological data) and additionally four SGE assays for three other cancer susceptibility genes for which pathogenicity is also presumptively ascribed to loss-of-function.

Thirdly, we reviewed CSPECs for 112 genes, illustrating wide variability across ClinGen VCEPs in how truthsets are assembled and adherence to Brnich-assay-validation methodology.

These analyses substantiate the urgency of calls for clarity in standards to drive consistency in how truthsets for assay validation are defined, recognising the variable approaches previously and currently adopted by assay developers and VCEPs(21).

Mechanics of the Brnich-methodology

Inherent to consideration of the assembly and performance of truthsets is appreciation of the mechanics of the Brnich methodology for assay-level-validation. This is a Bayesian approach comprising generation of a likelihood ratio (odds path) from comparison of two likelihoods. Likelihood one is the prior probability, amongst the assembled truthset variants, of a given variant being pathogenic (essentially the starting ratio of pathogenic truthset variants: benign truthset variants). Likelihood two is the posterior probability, namely that a variant assigned by the assay as deleterious is 'truly' pathogenic (accordingly to the truthset classification). The ratio of these likelihoods (likelihood ratio or odds path) thus quantifies the evidence weight for assay predictiveness for pathogenicity. A corresponding value is calculated for assay predictiveness for benignity. Logarithmic conversion of the likelihood ratio (odds path) to a $\log_{2.08}$ likelihood ratio (LLR) yields the assay-level Brnich-evidence score (EPs).

The first key feature of the Brnich-methodology is incorporation of a (+1) to the denominator for the posterior probability, with the stated intent of curbing infinity results(2). This results in attenuation of the likelihood ratio (odds path), which is increasingly punitive with smaller truthsets. The second important feature of the Brnich methodology is the paradoxical relationship whereby the $\text{Odds-Path}_{\text{pathogenicity}}$ (and thus $\text{LLR}_{\text{pathogenicity}}/\text{EP}_{\text{pathogenicity}}$) is primarily

influenced by the size of the benignity truthset whilst the $\text{Odds-Path}_{\text{benignity}}$ (and thus $\text{LLR}_{\text{benignity}}/\text{EP}_{\text{benignity}}$) is primarily influenced by the size of the pathogenicity truthset. It is a consequence of these two features, that when undertaking Brnich-validation using high-stringency ClinVar-derived missense variants, the paucity of benign truthset variants means the $\text{EP}_{\text{pathogenicity}}$ attainable is typically low even where concordance is high.

Impact of truthset stringency and phenotype

Relaxation of truthset stringency would be predicted to result in lower accuracy, a greater number of spurious classifications and a lower overall ‘veracity’ for truthset classifications against ‘the actual truth’. Consistent with this prediction, the observed concordance with the assay outputs drops as truthset stringency is reduced. Varying laxity in classification stringency will therefore be self-correcting via regression to the null: it should not erroneously inflate the ACMG-EPs. However, whilst the poorer concordance negatively impacts the Brnich-evidence score, this may be counter-balanced by the benefit in power afforded by larger truthset numbers.

Similarly, for the *VHL* gene-assay dyad, restriction by phenotype against which variants are submitted to ClinVar resulted in improved concordance but with modest impact on Brnich-evidence score due to reduced power from reduced truthset numbers. Using a broader versus narrower phenotypic definition for truthset classifications would likewise be predicted to regress to the null.

Evolving a robust approach to assembling truthsets for clinical validation of assays

Taking the common usecase whereby loss-of-function is the presumptive single mechanism of pathogenicity of all variants in the gene and is purported to be measured by the assay in question, we propose clinical validation of such assays should be based on three foundational principles.

Principle A: The critical objective is to confirm assay predictiveness for missense variants, as this is the variant type for which EPs from assay data are most likely to influence variant classification.

Examination of a mixture of variants (eg 'all' ClinVar variants) is not sufficiently informative as poor concordance for missense variants could be obscured via dilution (especially where missense variant numbers are small).

Principle B: Truthsets can be constructed using any ClinVar classification stringency, on the basis that reduced 'veracity' of a set of truthset variants (secondary to reduced stringency) is self-correcting through regression to the null. Furthermore, the benign missense truthsets can be augmented using variants systematically-classified using ACMG/AMPv3.0 rules, again applying a stringency that best optimises the $EP_{\text{pathogenicity}}$ (through concordance-power trade-off). The truthset selected should be that which best optimises the $EP_{\text{pathogenicity}}$ (through concordance-power trade-off). This will vary gene by gene, according to the constituency of ClinVar, which truthset assembly approach best optimises concordance versus power (ie yields the highest Brnich-evidence score (EPs)).

Principle C: Assay predictiveness for pathogenicity and for benignity can be considered separately. For a variant with limited additional information aside from functional data, erroneous classification as pathogenic is likely more clinically consequential than erroneous classification as benign. Furthermore, aberration of only a single mechanism is required for a variant to be demonstrated as pathogenic whilst to be benign all potential mechanisms of pathogenicity must be excluded.

Thus, Brnich-evidence scores (EPs) for the assay should be evaluated via a truthset comprising missense variants. As many truthsets of different stringency should be evaluated as feasible, retaining the outputs from the analysis by which the highest EP score is generated (separately for each of pathogenicity and benignity). We illustrate in Table S4 the EPs that would be awardable using this approach for the VHL, BRCA1, BRCA2 and RAD51C assays.

Limitations of analyses

The range of approaches to generating truthsets explored was not exhaustive. The endeavour is limited by the inherent paradox of using concordance with assay data to evaluate the veracity of truthsets, without knowing ‘the actual truth’. The number and veracity of variants attaining different stringency rankings in ClinVar will vary by gene, driven by age and quality of classification guidance, availability of informative clinical data and gene length and constraint. The range of associated phenotypes against which variants are submitted and their relationship to genotype will also vary by gene and may require more complex evaluation where different mechanisms of pathogenicity are implicated.

However, the principles we illustrate are universal regarding regression to the null and the inherent trade-off between stringency and power: these recommendations for assay validation thus pertain across genes of presumptive loss-of-function mechanism, regardless of specifics in ClinVar differences .

Future considerations for clinical validation of functional assays

The assay-level validation methodology described by Brnich et al produces a dichotomous assay-level output, thus not reflecting the continuum of variant-specific assay-scores. As we have illustrated for *VHL* and *RAD51C*, the Brnich-validation-framework can be applied for selected zones of deleteriousness as delineated by assay authors. In principle each deleterious output zone could be analysed using the Brnich-validation-framework as if were a stand-alone assay. However, for other recently published assays, authors have applied mixture modelling approaches, by which the assay outputs are modelled as corresponding to likelihoods: thus variant-specific scores (or numbers of EPs) can be assigned dependent on each variant’s assay output value. Notably, these approaches effectively calibrate and validate simultaneously, and are thus not reliant on author-prespecified thresholds. However, compared to the Brnich-validation-methodology, mixture modelling methods are less transparent and may not be readily

locally reproducible by diagnostic laboratory scientists. If the community were to transition from Brnich-assay-level clinical validation to variant-level clinical validation of functional assays, international consensus and clear guidance regarding accepted methodology will be required. It may be more practical to establish a trusted central body to undertake these clinical validation of new assays and/or support VCEPs in regard of application of methodology(3, 4).

Conclusion

Based on examination of 2,122 different truthsets across multiple genes, we provide consensus guidance from CanVIG-UK regarding truthsets for Brnich-assay-level validation. We propose that this approach provides robustness in capturing assay predictiveness for missense variants and is applicable to both small-scale and large-scale assays. Whilst also addressing, in evidence-based fashion, the challenge of limited numbers of ClinVar missense truthset variants through flexibility regarding (i) ClinVar classification stringency (ii) augmentation with systematically-generated ACMG classifications.

Availability of data and materials

The code used during this study are available at [TBC]. The ClinVar datasets used and/or analysed during the current study are available in the ClinVar repository, <https://ftp.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pub/clinvar/>. The functional assay datasets analysed during the current study are available in their respective published articles [and their supplementary information files] (VHL: [https://doi.org/10.1038/s41588-024-01800-z\(6\)](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41588-024-01800-z(6)); *BRCA1* [https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-018-0461-z\(7\)](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-018-0461-z(7)) and interim short report available at https://www.cangene-canvaruk.org/_files/ugd/ed948a_0399a952a1dc4767bed4364a04f6408b.pdf; *BRCA2*: [https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-024-08349-1\(9\)](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-024-08349-1(9));

RAD51C: [https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cell.2024.08.039\(8\)](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cell.2024.08.039(8))). All other data generated or analysed during the current study are included in this published article [and its supplementary information files].

Competing interests

[TBC]

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Author contributions

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